

1985 Feb 22

(To be published in the proceedings of the Second F.A.S.T. Thinkshop)

GREAT-CIRCLE REDUCTION BY THE NORTHERN DATA ANALYSIS CONSORTIUM (NDAC)

L. Lindegren¹ and C. Petersen²

¹Lund Observatory, Sweden

²Copenhagen University Observatory, Denmark

ABSTRACT

In a 12 hour interval, the HIPPARCOS satellite will observe some 1800 stars in a circular strip around the sky with a maximum width of 3° . The Great Circle Reduction will produce a single normal point, called abscissa, for each star in the interval. A least-squares solution takes as input the instantaneous object coordinates on the modulating grid and determines, in addition to the abscissae, the precise attitude motion in the scanning direction and the grid-to-field coordinate transformation. The paper describes the basic observation equations, solution method, and data management system used by NDAC.

1. INTRODUCTION

The HIPPARCOS instrument is basically capable of measuring one-dimensional instantaneous coordinates of celestial objects with respect to the primary grid. These depend on: (i) the proper direction of the object, in some reference system, at the instant of observation; (ii) the attitude or orientation of the telescope with respect to that same system; and (iii) the transformation from directions relative to the optical system to the geometrical pattern of the grid, the so-called field-to-grid transformation. Each of these characteristics of the object and instrument can be modelled very accurately by means of a finite set of parameters: the astrometric parameters of the object, the spline coefficients or similar describing the attitude angles as functions of time, and the polynomials representing the field-to-grid transformation.

Ideally, one would like to treat all these parameters as unknowns in a general solution encompassing the entire mission. Such an approach would present no mathematical difficulties, but the practical problems appear insurmountable at present, even if some efficient hierarchical blocking can be found. The two-level decomposition into independent Great Circle Reductions (*set solutions*) and a uniting Sphere

Reconstitution (*global solution*), which is used by both FAST and NDAC, is merely an approximation to the strict method. In defining certain intermediate quantities known as the *abscissae*, it takes maximum advantage of several very specific properties of the instrument and its operation. (The satellite was indeed designed with precisely this decomposition in mind.) The abscissa summarizes the astrometric information gathered on a particular object in a limited time interval (*set*) of about 6 to 12 hours. The circumstances and assumptions justifying this decomposition are in outline as follows:

(A) A sensible "mean coordinate direction" can be defined for any object in the set. For a *single star*, this is simply the coordinate direction of the star at the set mid-time (T_j). Any change of the coordinate direction in the course of the set, due to parallax and proper motion, will be completely linear to sub-milliarcsec accuracy. [In contrast, the proper direction (Murray, 1983) obtained by applying gravitational light deflection and stellar aberration, will exhibit significant non-linear variations over a few hours. These are however explicitly computable from known data (ephemerides) and do not depend perceptibly on the astrometric parameters.] For a *double star*, the mean coordinate direction refers to some photocentre of the object (not always the barycentre of the light), which is fairly well-defined under reasonable conditions. Even a *minor planet* can be treated in the same manner if it is formally regarded as a different object each time it enters the combined field of view, since the variation in coordinate direction is again linear over 20 s (the field crossing), but not over the entire set.

(B) The attitude control law is such that the Z axis (normal to the viewing directions) moves by not more than 2.6° in 12 hours. This is also the maximum spread in position angle of the different scans across a given object. Moreover, it is possible to select a Reference Great Circle (RGC) for the set, coinciding within a fraction of a degree with the mean scanning direction across most objects. Provided we have *some* positional information perpendicular to the RGC, we may regard these scans as measuring only the coordinate *along* the circle, that is, the abscissa. We need the perpendicular coordinate (ordinate) to about 0.1 arcsec and the motion of Z with respect to the RGC pole with similar accuracy (from the Attitude Reconstitution), for which purposes at least part of the set and global solutions must be iterated.

(C) The field-to-grid transformation is fully determinable within a set. This presupposes that it is stable over several hours and mathematically representable in terms of a moderate number of free parameters, and that the set is sufficiently long and uninterrupted. For instance, to determine the basic angle (formally one of the transformation parameters) one needs a closed chain of measurement along the circle, while the grid orientation requires that the same objects are observed in different parts of the field. A similar condition applies to the attitude determination about the Z axis (Ω ; see Paper I): it

must be completely determinable within the set. In practice this probably means that some degradation of the attitude accuracy must be accepted near the boundaries of the set. Choosing these boundaries to coincide with natural interruptions (occultations) will minimize this effect.

2. DEFINITIONS

In Paper I (Lindgren and van Leeuwen, 1985) we defined the time coordinate T and the equatorial and telescope triads $N = [l \ m \ n]$ and $Z = [x \ y \ z]$, and also the field index and field coordinates (f, w, z) of an object with respect to the telescope triad. In the following, the indices i, j, k designate respectively the object, set, and observation frame (interval of 2.133 s).

The set reference triad $R_j = [p_j \ q_j \ r_j]$ is defined by the transformation

$$R_j = N A_3(\alpha_j + \frac{1}{2}\pi) A_1(\frac{1}{2}\pi - \delta_j) A_3(c_j) \quad (1)$$

(Fig. 1), where (α_j, δ_j) is the pole of the RGC and c_j the abscissa zero-point correction (a small angle, as yet unknown). If $\bar{u}_i$ is the coordinate direction of an object, then the abscissa and ordinate, a_{ij}, o_{ij} , are given by

$$\bar{u}_i = p_j \cos o_{ij} \cos a_{ij} + q_j \cos o_{ij} \sin a_{ij} + r_j \sin o_{ij} \quad (2)$$

The field coordinates of object i at the mid-time of frame k , (w_{ik}, z_{ik}) , are given by Eqn (2) of Paper I in terms of the proper direction and the telescope triad. The grid coordinate G_{ik} designates a position strictly related to the primary grid, being zero at the centre of the middle slit (near $w = 0$) and increasing by +1 for each new slit in the direction of increasing w_{ik} (Fig. 2). The input for the set solution is actually the *smoothed* grid coordinate, free from the local irregularities of the physical grid.

The transformation from (w_{ik}, z_{ik}) to G_{ik} is provisionally of the following form, involving 11 achromatic and 5 chromatic coefficients:

$$\begin{aligned} G_{ik} = & \pm h_{00} + (g_{10} \pm h_{10})w_{ik} + (g_{01} \pm h_{01})z_{ik} + (g_{20} \pm h_{20})w_{ik}^2 + \\ & + (g_{11} \pm h_{11})w_{ik}z_{ik} + (g_{02} \pm h_{02})z_{ik}^2 + \\ & + C_i \left[\pm h'_{00} + (g'_{10} \pm h'_{10})w_{ik} + (g'_{01} \pm h'_{01})z_{ik} \right] \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

Upper/lower sign refers to the preceding/following field ($f = \pm 1$); $C_i = (B-V) - 0.5$ is the colour index of the object. It should be noted

that the expression contains no constant term: the constraints $g_{00} = g'_{00} = 0$ are implied and effectively define the origin of w as function of colour. For objects without a known $B-V$, we have to put $C_i = 0$ or some other assumed value.

3. THE OBSERVATION EQUATION

The observed grid coordinate of object i at frame mid-time T_k , obtained by the image location process, will be compared with a calculated grid coordinate based on the current knowledge of the abscissa, attitude, and field-to-grid transformation. The procedure is as follows.

For each object included in the set, we represent its abscissa and ordinate at the arbitrary time T by means of the formulae

$$a_{ij}(T) = a_{ij}^{(ref)} + (T - T_j) \dot{a}_{ij}^{(ref)} \quad (4)$$

$$o_{ij}(T) = o_{ij}^{(ref)} \quad (5)$$

where T_j is the set mid-time. $a_{ij}^{(ref)}$, $\dot{a}_{ij}^{(ref)}$, $o_{ij}^{(ref)}$ are initially calculated from the current star catalogue; in the subsequent processing of the set, *only* $a_{ij}^{(ref)}$ is subject to updating. From the sub-catalogue containing these three numbers per object in the set, we calculate the coordinate direction at time T_k by use of (4) - (5) and (2), assuming $c_j = 0$. Application of gravitational deflection and aberration then gives the proper direction.

From the Attitude Reconstitution (Paper I) we have also the three angles ν_k , ξ_k , Ω_k at frame mid-time, except that $\delta\Omega_k = 0$ has to be assumed in (I.3c). Using (I.1) we get the telescope triad at frame mid-time, $Z_k = NA_k$, and hence the field coordinates from (I.2). The calculated grid coordinate is finally obtained via the transformation (3) above.

The unknowns in the set solution are now: (i) the abscissae at the set mid-time, $a_{ij}^{(ref)}$; (ii) the attitude correction $\delta\Omega_k$ of each frame; and (iii) the 16 transformation coefficients in (3), d_m , $m = 1$ to 16 for brevity. The observation equation for object i in frame j is therefore

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial G_{ik}}{\partial a_{ij}} \Delta a_{ij}^{(ref)} + \frac{\partial G_{ik}}{\partial \Omega_k} \Delta \delta\Omega_k + \sum_m \frac{\partial G_{ik}}{\partial d_m} \Delta d_m + \text{noise} &= \\ &= G_{ik}^{(obs)} - G_{ik}^{(calc)} + n \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$\Delta a_{ij}^{(\text{ref})}$, $\Delta \delta \Omega_k$, and Δd_m are corrections (updatings) to the unknowns and n a small integer to correct for slit errors. Initial values for the unknowns are taken from the current star catalogue (abscissae) or the previous set solution (transformation coefficients), or set equal to zero (attitude).

In (6) we have written $\delta \Omega_k$ as an independent unknown for each frame. This corresponds to the simple and conservative case of the "geometrical" set solution, which will be used at least in the first iterations, until improved star positions have been obtained and most slit errors removed. In later solutions it is necessary however to take advantage of the smooth attitude motion between jet firings, and introduce some kind of numerical smoothing. The attitude corrections in a certain interval of several consecutive frames, called a *superframe*, are then connected by a polynomial of low degree. The coefficients of this polynomial replace the $\delta \Omega_k$ in the observation equation. The geometrical solution can be seen as the degenerate case when each superframe contains only one frame, and the degree of the polynomial is zero. To be meaningful, the number of frames per superframe divided by the number of free parameters per superframe should be of the order of 10 or higher. The superframes of course must not include the instants of jet firings.

4. LEAST-SQUARES SOLUTION

The structure of (6) is such that each observation equation contains exactly one abscissa unknown, the attitude unknowns of exactly one superframe, and all the transformation coefficients. In a 12 hour set there are about 1800 abscissae, some 400 to 20,000 attitude unknowns (depending on the degree of numerical smoothing), and 16 field-to-grid transformation unknowns. In order to get a manageable system of normal equations, one could eliminate either the attitude unknowns or the abscissae. The first method is more advantageous for the geometrical solution and with a moderate degree of numerical smoothing, while the second is better for maximum smoothing. However, since we will use the geometrical solution at least initially, we prefer to eliminate the attitude throughout. (There is also a possibility to use posterior smoothing of the geometrical solution as a means of iterative improvement.)

Presently the mechanics of the elimination process is briefly described. Let κ denote a superframe ($\kappa = k$ for the geometrical solution) and, in matrix notation,

$$B_{\kappa} \Delta \Omega_{\kappa} + C_{\kappa} \Delta a + v_{\kappa} = e_{\kappa} \quad (7)$$

the complete collection of observation equations (6) pertinent to the superframe. For simplicity we disregard slit errors here and take the transformation unknowns $\{d_m\}$ together with the abscissae in the vector

Δa . The equations are of course weight normalized so that $\text{Cov}(v_{\kappa}) = 1$. Note that C_{κ} is a very sparse matrix. Having thus collected all observations of a superframe, we form the corresponding part of the normals,

$$P \Delta \Omega + Q \Delta a = f \quad (8a)$$

$$Q' \Delta \Omega + M \Delta a = g \quad (8b)$$

with $P = B'B$, $Q = B'C$, $M = C'C$, $f = B'e$, $g = C'e$ (dropping subscript κ). Now let $F'F$ be the Cholesky factorization of the small positive definite matrix P (F is upper-triangular). Performing the Cholesky factorization is formally equivalent to premultiplying by F'^{-1} , and the reduced form of (8a) is therefore

$$F \Delta \Omega + (F'^{-1}Q) \Delta a = (F'^{-1}f) \quad (9)$$

Solving for the attitude unknowns in terms of Δa and inserting in (8b) yields the system

$$[M - (F'^{-1}Q)'(F'^{-1}Q)] \Delta a = g - (F'^{-1}Q)'(F'^{-1}f) \quad (10)$$

in which the attitude unknowns have been eliminated. Since these unknowns particular to the superframe κ will not appear in future observations, we can add (10) to the normal equations for Δa being built up. Note that M is a diagonal matrix (with a narrow border for the transformation unknowns), but the modification in (10) introduces off-diagonal elements (i_1, i_2) as soon as the two objects i_1, i_2 appear together in some superframe.

Accumulating (10) for all superframes in a set results in a sparse system of normal equations for the ~ 1800 abscissae and transformation coefficients. This is stored columnwise, from the first non-zero element in each column down to the diagonal. Reordering of the abscissae according to Banker's algorithm (Snay, 1976) is employed to reduce the matrix profile (number of stored elements). The filling factor of the normal equations matrix (not counting the border for the transformation unknowns) is about 12% for the geometrical solution, increasing to 20% for superframes of 100 s length, and to 31% for 400 s superframes (Lund, 1984); this is the portion of the matrix that must be stored after reordering.

The equations for Δa are solved by the Cholesky method, arbitrarily keeping one abscissa fixed to provide the origin on the RGC and thus avoid singularity. Backsubstitution into (9) for each superframe could then give the attitude corrections. This last step can be avoided however by *preadjustment* of the attitude in an iterative least-squares solution. At the time when we have the sub-normals (9) for a certain superframe, we solve this small system for $\Delta \Omega_{\kappa}$ and adjust the attitude correspondingly by temporarily assuming $\Delta a = 0$. Since the solution is anyway iterated to the point where the correction vector

becomes negligible, there is no need to adjust the attitude any further. Moreover, the right-hand side of (10) becomes simply $= g$ in this process, since the rhs in (9) after preadjustment is $= 0$.

The (unknown) integer n was introduced in (6) to account for the slit errors, *i.e.* cases when the grid coordinate (observed or calculated) is wrong by a whole number of slit periods due to the 2π phase ambiguity of the modulated signal. In the set solution, only *slit inconsistencies* can be detected and removed, that is when the slit error on a given object is not the same in all observations of it. The following method is used to remove slit inconsistencies. Let ΔG_{ik} be the grid coordinate difference (observed - calculated) in the right member of (6). While forming the observation equations, an array r_i is set up, with $r_i = \Delta G_{ik}$ if k is the first frame in which object i appears. In subsequent observations, we choose

$$n = \text{NINT}(r_i - \Delta G_{ik}) \quad (11)$$

where $\text{NINT}()$ is the nearest-integer function. It is easy to see that this procedure immediately eliminates all slit inconsistencies, if the peak-to-valley error due to the attitude, transformation, and observation noise is less than $\frac{1}{2}$ slit period (0.6 arcsec). However, larger errors can be accommodated in an iterative solution. From numerical simulations it appears that the practical requirement is an *rms* attitude error in Ω of not more than 0.2 arcsec. A better choice for r_i is probably the average ΔG_{ik} for all frames including object i , which however requires an extra pass through the observations.

5. IMPLEMENTATION AND THE DATA MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The set solutions will be run on a dedicated HP 9000 computer located at the Danish Space Research Institute in Lyngby (Copenhagen). Tapes with grid coordinates, attitude data, and catalogue updates (from the star mapper observations) are regularly received from the British group at Royal Greenwich Observatory (Herstmonceux). All programs are written in FORTRAN 77 and run under the UNIX operating system.

The large amount of data involved in the set solutions and the large number of times the program is to be executed makes it necessary to have a data management system to control the storage of these data and the setting up of input data and parameters for the solution process, and to monitor the progress of the solutions. This system is largely defined by the organization and contents of the major data files and tapes involved, and by a restricted set of operations that can be performed on them. Such operations include copying data from tape to disc and back, setting up an input file for the solution program, scheduling the solution, and copying output data to tape. The data management system is divided into two parts, one controlling the input data ("observations") and the other controlling the sets.

Obviously, the amount of observations involved cannot be kept permanently on disc. But it is not convenient either to have the solution program read data directly from tapes. Consequently, a number of permanent disc files are reserved for data which are to be processed in the near future. Observations on the tapes from RGO are converted to the proper format and stored on these files, which are however also copied to tapes for security reasons and because the observations may be processed again later. A number of catalogues permanently residing on the disc contain information about all observation files and tapes available to the system, and allow any observation (identified by its type, observation time, and RGO processing time) to be retrieved from the disc or, if the record is on tape only, to return the required tape and file number. If several versions of the same observations exist, the latest version (according to RGO processing time) is normally used.

A set is defined by selecting the set interval and RGC pole, which can be made either automatically or by manual intervention. A set input file is initialized by copying to it the corresponding observations, *a priori* instrument parameter values, etc. After the set solution process, the set file contains also the updated abscissae and other information describing how the set was processed. The same file may be used as input for additional passes of the set solution, if required, and the entire file is therefore saved on tape. The solution process can be scheduled as soon as all input data have been collected in the set file.

During the processing of a set, a temporary work file is used to contain the observation equations and normal equations. The disc may hold more than one set file and work file at a time, as several solution processes could run in parallel. The set solution process can be divided into a number of tasks, each of which creates or updates one or more data types in the set or work file as function of other data types. The corresponding software modules all have access to certain global set parameters and to a work area used as buffer space for the data. The main modules of the set solution program are: initialization - make list of objects and coordinates - reordering - set up column and block tables for the normals - form observation equations - form normal equations - Cholesky factorization - solution of right-hand sides - update abscissae and transformation coefficients.

REFERENCES

- Lindgren, L and van Leeuwen, F, 1985, *Attitude Reconstitution by the NDAC*, in this volume (= Paper I)
- Lindgren, L, and Söderhjelm, S, 1985, *Sphere Reconstitution by the NDAC*, in this volume (= Paper III)

Lund, N, 1984, *Re-ordering and Dynamical Smoothing of Simulated HIPPARCOS data* (unpublished note 1984 Feb 13, NDAC-C120)

Murray, C A, 1983, *Vectorial Astrometry*, Ch. 2.5, Adam Hilger

Snay, R E, 1976, *Reducing the profile of sparse symmetric matrices*, Bull. Géodésique, Vol. 50, No. 94

Figure 1. Definition of the set reference triad $R_j = [p_j \ q_j \ r_j]$ and the abscissa, ordinate (a, o) of an object.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the field coordinates (w, z) and (grossly exaggerated) the grid coordinate G , taking integer values at the slit centres.